

Effect of Yoga on Anxiety Levels in Working Women

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Abstract

Today Yoga, Sports are regarded as a Prestigious national concept and numerous scientific studies have been conducted on the subject. Humans are inherently competitive creatures who strive for perfection in their athletic endeavors. In order to prove their supremacy, Women compete against each other. Research laboratories have grown in size, complexity and number which have fueled the study of yoga. The current study compares the level of anxiety among female intercollegiate. Anxiety is one of the most pressing issues of today's science. Women's anxieties are exacerbated by cultural Conflicts, Economic hardships and industrialization. We planned to undertake a study of effect of yoga on anxiety score before and after yoga training in apparently health working women. The study was carried out in 35 apparently healthy working women aged between 25 to 40 years who attended three months of yoga training. State and trait anxiety scale was used to evaluate anxiety level before and after yoga training. Our study showed a statistically significant difference in total anxiety score before and after yoga training by applying paired 'T' test. We concluded that regular practice of yoga in day life reduces anxiety levels and improves subjective feeling of wellbeing. Our study thus helps to popularize yoga among working women.

Keywords: Stress, Yoga, Anxiety Scale, T-Test

Introduction

Today working women are constantly under stress to maintain balance between home and workplace. This stress affects their physical and mental health; but Stress is necessary for life. We need stress for creativity, learning and for survival. Stress is only harmful when it becomes overwhelming and interrupts the healthy state of equilibrium. Stress jacks up the nervous system, overburdens the adrenal glands and lowers immunity. Yoga is considered to be one of the most important, effective and valuable tools available for man to overcome various physical and psychological problems.

Objective

Humanity has become more critical, inventive, sensitive, and obsessed as a result of scientific and technological advancements. Because of this, there was a rise in stress levels. The contemporary sickness is advancing at an ever-increasing rate in the current planet. Stress. Stress has taken a serious toll on my health... Many of the issues afflicting humanity are the result of self-inflicted causes. Relationship tension, workplace conflict over ego, and domestic problems are all regular occurrences in today's society, all of which add to the general sense of anxiety. Increasing workloads and an increasingly competitive work environment have left individuals with little time to care for and maintain their relationships and for frequent self-reflection. When we are frightened or overwhelmed, our bodies go into stress mode. Increasing home and work obligations have put a lot of individuals in a stressful position. Stress in one place might have an impact on stress levels in another. Hence, the present study was undertaken to see effect of yoga on state and trait anxiety before and after yoga training in healthy working women. The world would be a drab and boring place if it weren't for worry. While stress may have a negative impact on our physical and mental health, too much of it can. Up to 80% of sickness may be attributed to stress, and this is not new information. "All ailments of the body originate in the mind or spirit," Plato wrote more than 2,000 years ago.

Methodology

The study was conducted on 35 healthy female subjects aged between 25-40 years who attended two months of yoga training. All the subjects had never undergone any kind of yoga training earlier. The women were involved in professions, like Doctors, Engineers, Teachers and Bank managers. Institutional ethical committee clearance was obtained. The informed consent was obtained from all the participants. The yoga training was given one hour per day for two months which included.

- (a) Prayer: 1 min.
- (b) Sthihpragnyasana: 2 min.
- (c) Asanas: 25 min.
- (d) Anuloma, Ujjayi, Bhramari: 5 min.

- (e) Yognidra with visualization: 20 min.
- (f) Meditation on Onkar & Tratak: 5 min.
- (g) Prayer & Sthithpragnyasana: 2 min.

Spielberger's state and trait anxiety inventory was used to evaluate anxiety levels before and after yoga training. Spielberger state-trait anxiety inventory (STAI) is a forty- item Likert-type questionnaire designed to assess individual differences in the experience of anxiety. The trait form of the inventory assesses an individual's general anxiety level, and the state form of the inventory assesses the individual's anxiety specific to the time of completion of the survey. Each form consists of twenty items with total scores that range from a minimum of twenty to a maximum of eighty [3]. Statistical analysis was done by applying paired 't' test using Graph pad prism 5 software.

Results

Our study showed statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in total anxiety score before and after yoga training by applying paired 't' test.

Table 1: Change in state anxiety score

State Anxiety score Before yoga training (Mean±S.D)	Anxiety score After yoga training (Mean±S.D)	't' value	p' value	Significance
52.94±10.05	34.23±8.630	10.75	< 0.0001	Significant

Figure 1: Comparison of State Anxiety score

Table 2: Change in trait anxiety score

Trait Anxiety score Before yoga training (Mean±S.D)	Trait Anxiety score After yoga training (Mean±S.D)	't' value	'p' value	Significance
45.26±10.05	34.69±7.157	7.210	< 0.0001	Significant

Figure 2: Comparison of Trait Anxiety score

Table 3: Change in total anxiety score

Total Anxiety score Before yoga training (Mean±S.D)	Total Anxiety score After yoga training (Mean±S.D)	't' value	'p' value	Significance
97.91±17.14	69.20±13.87	t=10.82	< 0.0001	Significant

Figure 3: Comparison of Total Anxiety Score

Discussion

The tables 1, 2, 3 and figures 1, 2, 3 show significant reductions in Spielberger’s state, trait and total anxiety score after practicing yoga in working women. This demonstrates the beneficial effects of yoga for reducing stress. Stress affects women health in many ways. Stress is known to modulate activity of autonomic nervous system as well as central nervous system. In stressful states, there will be preponderance of sympathetic activity. This shift towards sympathetic may be the reason of anxiety (Srinivasan et al, 2006) [1]. Some common physical and emotional symptoms of stress are: Fatigue; Head, back, neck and shoulder aches; Stomach problems; Change in menstrual cycles; Feeling anxious; Feeling isolated; Frustration; Irritability and Difficulty in concentrating. Subtle discriminations at workplaces, family pressures and societal demands add to these stresses in them Yogic practices bring about stable autonomic nervous system with a tendency towards parasympathetic nervous system dominance. Some mechanisms have been proposed to explain how yoga reduces the anxiety level. Yoga breathing exercises decrease arousal, which calms and focuses the mind, relaxes the body, oxygenates the blood, soothes anxiety, and promotes clear thinking. The intense concentration and body control involved in breathing exercises help free the mind from mental distractions, worries, and fatigue.

Conclusion

Our study concludes that regular practice of yoga reduces anxiety levels and improves subjective feeling of wellbeing. Thus, our

study helps to popularize yoga among working women.

References

1. Bhupendra Singh, Jagdish. Effect of Yogic Practice on Anxiety. International Referred Research Journal, July, 2011. RNI-RAJBIL 2009/29954.VoL.III Issue-30, p-56-57.
2. David W. Orme-Johnson & John T. Farrow.Chakrabarti, Ghosh & Sahana's Human Physiology.2nd Ch.17 part- 3 Physiological changes during Meditation. P-1236-1244.
3. RL Bijlani, S Manjunatha. Understanding Medical Physiology.4th Ed, 2011. Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers(P) Ltd. Yoga p-747.
4. A.K Jain. Textbook of Physiology. 4th Ed. Avichal Publishing Company, 2009; Vol-1, Physiology of Yoga, p- 498-511.
5. Gupta et al, Effect of Yoga Based Lifestyle Intervention on State and Trait Anxiety. Indian J Physiol Pharmacol 2006; 50 (1): 41–47.
6. Mullur et al. Influence of Yoga Practice on Anxiety Level of Apparently Healthy Female Subjects of Bijapur (Karnataka). International Journal of Biomedical and Advance Research. 2012; 03(08), p-618-621.

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